

Meet the Expert: at Sudur Paschimanchal Academy

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Introduction

Sudur Paschimanchal Campus (SPC) emerges as a leading educational institution in the Sudurpaschim Province, committed to providing quality education, promoting research and innovation, and contributing to the socio-economic development of the region. The institution hosts regular "Meet the Expert" sessions, providing a platform for students to interact with renowned experts and professionals in their respective fields.

On August 1 -2, Sudur Paschimanchal Academy (SPA) hosted a "Meet the Expert" session at Santoshi Tole-2, Dhangadhi, Nepal. The session featured Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, a best management scientist in Nepal, as the resource person, with Mr. Jagan Joshi serving as the moderator. The event aimed to engage students in discussions about pressing issues affecting agriculture and society, particularly in the context of Nepal.

Major Concerns Discussed

The session covered a range of critical topics that reflect the current challenges and opportunities in Nepal, particularly concerning agriculture and societal development:

1. **Climate Change and Adversity:** Participants discussed the severe impacts of climate change, including water scarcity and reliance on ponds for irrigation. The quality of available water was

highlighted as a significant concern, with issues of salinity and odor affecting agricultural productivity.

Climate change refers to significant and long-term alterations in the Earth's climate patterns, including temperature, precipitation, wind patterns, and other atmospheric conditions.

These changes are primarily driven by human activities, such as the burning of fossil fuels (coal, oil, and natural gas), deforestation, industrial processes, and agricultural practices, which release greenhouse gases (GHGs) into the atmosphere.

The primary greenhouse gases responsible for climate change include carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and fluorinated gases. These gases trap heat in the Earth's atmosphere, leading to a gradual increase in global temperatures, a phenomenon known as global warming.

The insights from Mishra's works emphasize the critical intersection of climate change, occupational safety, and the need for adaptive strategies in various sectors. In his article "Climate Change: Occupational Safety and Health," Mishra (2024) discusses how climate change poses significant risks to occupational safety, highlighting the necessity for organizations to implement robust health and safety measures to protect workers in increasingly hazardous environments. This underscores the importance of integrating climate resilience into workplace policies to mitigate risks associated with extreme weather events and environmental changes. Furthermore, in "Government Investment in Agriculture and Policy Recommendations," Mishra (2024) advocates for increased government investment in the agricultural sector as a means to enhance productivity and sustainability. He argues that strategic policy frameworks are essential for fostering innovation and addressing the challenges posed by climate change, thereby ensuring food security and economic stability. Additionally, during the 4th Annual International Conference on "Harmony in Innovation," Mishra (2024) explored how emerging technologies and dynamic management strategies can facilitate adaptation to global business landscapes. He

emphasized the role of innovation in navigating challenges brought about by climate change and market volatility, suggesting that organizations must embrace technological advancements to remain competitive and resilient. Collectively, these works highlight the urgent need for integrated approaches that consider environmental sustainability, occupational health, and innovation in policy-making and organizational strategies to effectively address the multifaceted challenges posed by climate change.

2. **Harmful Convention Mindset:** The need to shift away from outdated mindsets that hinder progress was emphasized. The importance of adaptability and innovation in agricultural practices was underscored. The concept of maintaining a healthy and happy life is closely tied to sustainable agricultural practices, technological innovation, and economic stability. By prioritizing these elements, individuals and communities can work towards a more balanced and fulfilling lifestyle. Mishra's insights underscore the importance of integrating sustainable practices into everyday life, not only for personal health but also for the health of the planet and future generations.

3. **Forest Fires and Emerging Viruses:** The session addressed the increasing frequency of forest fires and the emergence of new viruses, linking these phenomena to broader environmental changes.
4. **Changing Human Lifestyles:** The discussion highlighted how modern lifestyles are evolving and the implications for agriculture and food consumption patterns.
5. **Advancements in Artificial General Intelligence:** The potential of artificial intelligence to transform various sectors, including agriculture, was explored, with an emphasis on the need for adaptation.
6. **Importance of Industry Over Information:** It was noted that without development in the industrial sector, mere information is insufficient for progress.
7. **Coping with Modern Technology:** The necessity for individuals and communities to adapt to rapidly advancing technologies was discussed.

8. **Technocratic Life:** The prevalence of a technocratic lifestyle was examined, emphasizing the need for balance between technology and traditional practices.
9. **Social Learning Process:** The importance of social learning in addressing contemporary challenges was highlighted as a vital component of progress.
10. **Digital Transformation and Sustainable Development:** The relationship between digital transformation and sustainable development was emphasized, suggesting that digital tools can enhance agricultural practices and promote sustainability.
11. **Student Unions as Business Platforms:** The potential for student unions to evolve into platforms for entrepreneurship and business development was discussed.
12. **Income Generating Programs:** The session explored various income-generating initiatives, including the establishment of a maid company in Delhi, emphasizing the importance of small, non-profit ventures.
13. **Entrepreneurship Opportunities:** The potential for both students and teachers to engage in entrepreneurial activities was encouraged, highlighting the role of education in fostering innovation.

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra shared his extensive body of work encompasses various aspects of project management, occupational safety, and the integration of technology in improving operational efficiency.

Key Insights

Sustainable Project Management: In his book "Global Contract Administration," Mishra (2020) emphasizes the importance of sustainable practices in project management. He advocates for frameworks that not only ensure compliance with contractual obligations but also promote environmental stewardship and social responsibility.

Innovative Approaches: Mishra's research on project management theory and practice highlights the need for innovative approaches in managing projects across different countries (Mishra, 2020). He explores how adapting global best practices can enhance local project outcomes, particularly in developing regions like Nepal.

Health and Safety: Mishra has addressed critical issues related to occupational safety and health, particularly in the context of construction projects. His work underscores the necessity of implementing robust safety protocols to protect workers and improve overall project efficiency (Mishra, 2024).

Technological Integration: In his discussions on emerging technologies, Mishra emphasizes that modern project management must incorporate technological advancements to remain

competitive. He argues that leveraging technology can lead to improved project delivery and sustainability (Mishra, 2024).

Socio-Economic Development: Mishra's research often intersects with socio-economic issues, advocating for policies that enhance the economic viability of projects while addressing community needs. His studies on foreign aid and its impact on Nepal's development highlight the importance of strategic investments in infrastructure and social programs (Mishra, 2021).

Educational Contributions: As an educator, Mishra has contributed significantly to the academic landscape, mentoring students and professionals in the principles of effective project management and sustainable practices. His publications serve as valuable resources for understanding the complexities of managing projects in diverse environments.

Key Insights on Housing and Construction

- 1. Housing Needs for Low-Income Groups:** In his article "Housing Needs Fulfillment for Low-Income Group," Mishra (2019) discusses the critical need for affordable housing solutions in Nepal. He highlights that a substantial portion of the population struggles to access adequate housing, which is essential for improving living standards and overall quality of life. Mishra advocates for targeted policies that address the specific needs of low-income families, ensuring they have access to safe and affordable housing options.
- 2. Risk Management in Construction Projects:** Mishra's research on risk management practices in housing development emphasizes the necessity of identifying and mitigating risks to ensure project success (Mishra & Aithal, 2021). He argues that effective risk management strategies are crucial for minimizing delays and cost overruns, which are common challenges in the construction industry. By implementing robust risk assessment frameworks, stakeholders can enhance project outcomes and ensure the safety and satisfaction of residents.
- 3. Compliance with Building Regulations:** In the study "Compliance Status of Building Bylaws and Codes in High-rise Apartment Buildings of Nepal," Mishra et al. (2021) examine the adherence to building regulations in the construction of high-rise structures. Their findings indicate that non-compliance with safety standards poses significant risks to occupants. Mishra emphasizes the importance of strict enforcement of building codes to enhance safety and sustainability in urban development.
- 4. Sustainable Construction Practices:** Mishra advocates for the adoption of sustainable construction practices that minimize environmental impact while maximizing resource efficiency. His work highlights the need for integrating eco-friendly materials and technologies into the construction process, which can lead to long-term benefits for both the environment and the community (Mishra & Aithal, 2021).
- 5. Technological Integration:** Mishra discusses the role of modern technology in enhancing construction efficiency and safety. He encourages the use of innovative construction techniques

and materials to improve the overall quality and durability of housing projects. By embracing technological advancements, the construction sector can better meet the growing demand for housing while addressing sustainability concerns.

6. Mr. Jagan Nath Joshi , head of IQAC of SPC highlighted some of his readings from Dr. Mishra's as 'Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's research contributions have significantly impacted the fields of housing and construction, particularly within the context of Nepal. His work addresses critical issues such as labor productivity, cost-effectiveness, quality assessment, and risk management in construction projects, providing valuable insights for stakeholders in the industry. One notable study by Mishra and Maskey (2018) focuses on the assessment of labor productivity within the Armed Police Force Nepal Building project. This research highlights the factors influencing labor efficiency, enabling project managers to optimize resource allocation and improve overall project performance (Mishra & Maskey, 2018). In another significant contribution, Mishra and Chaudhary (2018) conducted a cost-effectiveness assessment of various cement brands used in construction projects. This analysis aids stakeholders in making informed decisions regarding material selection, which can lead to cost savings and enhanced project outcomes (Mishra & Chaudhary, 2018). Mishra's work on quality assessment of construction materials is also noteworthy. For instance, his study on the quality of high-density polyethylene pipes used in water supply and sewerage projects ensures that high standards are maintained, ultimately benefiting end-users and promoting sustainable infrastructure development (Mishra et al., 2021). Furthermore, Mishra has explored the causes of disputes in international competitive bidding for road contracts funded by the Asian Development Bank. His findings shed light on the challenges faced by project teams and provide strategies for effective conflict resolution, which is crucial for minimizing delays and cost overruns in construction projects (Mishra et al., 2021). In addition to these contributions, Mishra's research on occupational hazards during construction projects emphasizes the importance of prioritizing worker safety and implementing robust risk management strategies (Mishra & Aithal, 2021). His work highlights the need for a comprehensive approach to safety in high-risk environments, ensuring the well-being of workers and the successful completion of projects. Overall, Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's research has made significant contributions to the housing and construction sectors, providing essential insights and practical solutions for enhancing productivity, quality, and safety in construction projects in Nepal.' further he closed the program with vote of thanks.

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Conclusions

The "Meet the Expert" session provided a valuable platform for students to engage with pressing issues facing Nepal, particularly in agriculture and socio-economic development. Dr. Mishra's insights emphasized the need for a paradigm shift in agricultural practices and societal attitudes to address the challenges posed by climate change, technological advancements, and changing lifestyles. The discussions underscored the importance of adapting to modern realities while preserving traditional

knowledge and practices. The potential for entrepreneurship and innovation within the student body was particularly encouraging, suggesting that the next generation can play a crucial role in shaping Nepal's agricultural and economic landscape. Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's work reflects a deep commitment to advancing project management practices through sustainability, innovation, and a focus on health and safety. His insights are crucial for professionals seeking to navigate the challenges of modern project environments while contributing to the broader goals of socio-economic development.

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's insights into housing and construction underscore the importance of addressing the needs of low-income groups, implementing effective risk management strategies, ensuring compliance with building regulations, and adopting sustainable practices. His research serves as a valuable resource for policymakers, construction professionals, and stakeholders aiming to improve the housing landscape in Nepal.

Suggestions

Based on the discussions held during the session, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Promote Sustainable Agricultural Practices:** Encourage the adoption of sustainable farming techniques that are resilient to climate change and enhance productivity.
2. **Enhance Water Management Systems:** Invest in improved irrigation and water management systems to address water scarcity and ensure the availability of quality water for agricultural use.
3. **Foster Innovation and Entrepreneurship:** Create programs that support students in developing entrepreneurial skills and launching innovative agricultural ventures.
4. **Encourage Digital Literacy:** Implement training programs to enhance digital literacy among students and farmers, enabling them to leverage technology for agricultural development.
5. **Strengthen Community Engagement:** Promote community-based initiatives that encourage collective action in addressing local agricultural challenges and fostering socio-economic development.
6. **Support Research and Development:** Advocate for increased investment in agricultural research and development to explore new technologies and practices that can improve productivity and sustainability.
7. **Facilitate Knowledge Sharing:** Establish platforms for knowledge sharing among students, farmers, and experts to foster collaboration and innovation in agricultural practices.

By implementing these suggestions, stakeholders can work toward creating a more sustainable and prosperous agricultural sector in Nepal, ultimately contributing to the overall development of the country.

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Moderator: Mr. Jagan Nath Joshi is an accomplished academician with over 22 years of teaching experience. He currently serves as an Assistant Professor and the Head of the Internal Quality Assurance Department (IQAC) at Sudur Paschimanchal Campus. In addition to his teaching responsibilities, Joshi is the Managing Editor of SP: SWAG journal, a publication dedicated to scholarly work.

Throughout his career, Joshi has demonstrated a strong commitment to education and research. His extensive experience in the field has allowed him to make significant contributions to the academic community. As the IQAC Head, he plays a crucial role in ensuring the quality and continuous improvement of the institution's educational processes.

Joshi's dedication to his work is evident in his role as the Managing Editor of SP: SWAG journal. In this position, he oversees the publication of scholarly articles and research papers, promoting the dissemination of knowledge and fostering academic discourse.

With his impressive teaching experience and leadership roles, Jagan Nath Joshi continues to make a positive impact on the educational landscape. His commitment to excellence and his contributions to the field of academia are commendable.

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Resource Person: Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra is a distinguished scholar with a Doctorate in Project Management from Kanpur University, where he focused on Project Performance Assessment in Terms of Time, Cost, and Quality of Bridge Construction Projects. He also holds a post doctorate in Operational Analysis of Projects in Nepal. He is further doing his D.Litt on Safe Building Project Operation as highest academic research degree. Currently, Dr. Mishra serves as a Professor at Kathmandu College of Management, United Technical College. He is a regular visiting faculty, thesis supervisor, and research professor at various institutions, including Myaglung Campus Teraththum Institute of Engineering, Puichowk, Dharan, Lumbini Engineering, Gaurishanker Campus, Apex College, Srinivas University and Lincoln University and Management Science College, Rupandehi. Dr. Mishra has held positions as an associate professor and research director at Joint Constituent College of Pokhara University. He is the Editor-in-Chief of DV Publication, India, and serves on the editorial boards of several journals published

by colleges in Nepal. Additionally, he is a member of various scientific societies, such as the South Asia Institute of Science and Engineering (SAISE), Fellow of the SAS Society, Member of the Operation Research Society of Nepal, and Country Coordinator of the International American Council for Research and Development (IACRD). Dr. Mishra's expertise has been recognized through numerous awards and honors bestowed by national and international organizations. He has published 17 international reference books and has been a chief guest, organizer, speaker, and advisor for various conferences. He holds 25 Intellectual Property Rights from the Government of India and 6 patents including United Kingdom and India With an impressive publication record of over 200 peer-reviewed research articles, Dr. Mishra has presented at 15 international conferences and numerous national conferences. He supervises theses for universities such as Lincoln University, Malaysia, Srinivas University, India, and Tribhuvan and Pokhara University of Nepal. He serves as an external examiner for research work at various universities and as a keynote speaker at local and international conferences. Dr. Mishra's research projects are supported by governmental and private organizations in Nepal. He is an advisory board member of different international journals published by universities. Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's commitment to occupational safety, sustainability, and development project management has been instrumental in driving progress and innovation in these critical areas. His research and contributions have left an indelible mark on the industries and communities he has served, making him a respected and influential figure in his field.

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's impactful research made him to represent AD Scientific index as **best management scientist in Nepal**.

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